

ANALYSIS OF THE OPERATION OF A PUMPING SYSTEM USING A PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM WITH PVSYST SOFTWARE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13889224>

Abstract. *It is important to suggest that providing water pumps with energy in agriculture using renewable energy sources is one of the pressing issues. In the given research, the efficiency of the system and photovoltaic installation was assessed using PVsyst 7.4 software to create an intensive garden on 10 hectares of land in Surkhandarya region. A number of changes were made based on the capabilities of the program when creating a system simulation. The efficiency of the system in terms of water consumption was studied in terms of seasons. Results on energy losses and general conclusions were obtained.*

Keywords: *solar energy, pump, efficiency, solar station, performance, PVsyst, energy loss.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known to everyone that the percentage of renewable energy sources used worldwide is growing year by year [1-2]. There is no doubt that these figures will increase every year against the background of a reduction in the use of traditional fuels and a decrease in emissions of harmful gases emitted by mankind into the environment. Despite the fact that the use of solar energy in water pumps, which is one of the main sources of energy in agriculture, began many years ago [3-5], it remains one of the main trends today. It is important that the volume of energy obtained from renewable energy sources will exceed 316 GW by 2023, and the largest share of this energy will belong to photovoltaic stations [6]. With the use of irrigation pumps [7-8], the transition of harvesting methods to green energy continues worldwide [9-10]. At present time the transition to green energy is expanding in all areas. Due to the practice of efficient use of water on a global scale, drip irrigation has become widespread in practice [11-12].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

During the conducted research there was an opportunity to design the power supply of water pumps of a farm located in Surkhandarya region through a solar installation based on the existing capabilities of the PVsyst 7.4 program. Instead of a 4.4 kW station (8 by 550 W), installed in a real situation, we studied (10 by 440 W) based on the capabilities of the system. Two separate solar power plants installed on the farm provide electricity to water pumps (Fig. 1). In this case, the main pump takes water from a depth of 35-38 m and throws it into the main pool, and two pumps pump water into two upper pools. The main goal of our work is a comparative analysis of the efficiency of the pumping system and the photovoltaic system in water extraction from a stationary depth of 36 m. These activities were conducted based on the capabilities of the PVsyst 7.4 program, which is very typical in this area.

Definitely, after entering the geographic location data into the PVsyst software, it automatically loaded the radiation data and the required external parameters from the database. A

realistic value of 18 degrees was included for the tilt angle of the photovoltaic module. A summary of the information entered for programming by general parameters can be found in Figure 2.

Figure 1. General view of the photovoltaic system, main water pump and tank section.

General parameters			
Pumping PV System		Deep Well to Storage	
System Requirements	3.4 bar	Well characteristics	Storage tank
Static head		Static level depth	-32 m
Seasonal water needs		Specific drawdown	-1.67 m/m ³ /h
Summer (Jun-Aug)	Autumn (Sep-Nov)	Diameter	0 cm
60.00 m ³ /day	50.00 m ³ /day	Pump level	+62 m
Winter (Dec-Feb)	Spring (Mar-May)	Lower dynamic level	-41 m
5.00 m ³ /day	45.00 m ³ /day		
Hydraulic circuit		PV Field Orientation	
Piping length	50 m	Fixed plane	18 / 0 °
Pipes	PESO	Tilt/azimuth	
Dia	54 mm		
PV module		PV Array and Pump	
Manufacturer	Generic	Pump	Manufacturer
Model	Mono 440 Wp Twin 144 half-cells	Model	SP 3A-10 120V
Unit Name_Power	440 Wp	Pump Technology	Centrifugal Multistage
Number of PV modules	10 units	Motor	AC motor, biphased
Nominal (STC)	4400 Wp	Associated or integrated converter	
Modules	5 strings x 2 in series	Type	MPPT
At operating cond. (50°C)		Voltage range	100 - 140 V
Pmp	3998 Wp	Operating conditions	
U _{mp}	75 V	Head min.	2.34 m
I _{mp}	53 A	Head Nom	4.91 m
Total PV power		Head max.	6.97 m
Nominal (STC)	4.40 kWp	Corresp. Flowrate	5.08 m ³ /h
Total	10 modules	Resp. power	1500 W
Pumping system controller		Number of pumps	
System Operating Control	MPPT-4C inverter	pumps	2 in parallel
Power Conditioning Unit		Control device	
Type	MPPT-4C inverter	Manufacturer	Grundfos
Operating conditions		Model	SA 400 - 45V
Nominal power	3920 W	System Configuration	MPPT-4C inverter
Power (Theoretical)	39 W		
Max. efficiency	97.0 %		
EURO efficiency	95.0 %		
Minimum MPPT Voltage	50 V		
Maximum MPPT Voltage	100 V		
Maximum Array Voltage	116 V		
Maximum Input Current	61.9 A		

Figure 2. General parameters, photovoltaic array and pump system controller.

Since the results obtained with PVsyst 7.4 are presented on a large scale, we found it necessary to take those parts that we consider necessary for our work.

3. RESULTS

It is important to suggest that after entering the values for the required calculations, a report on the obtained value is automatically generated via the PVsyst 7.4 application. In addition, it will be possible to conduct an economic analysis. The main results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Main results.

The results show that the system efficiency is 17.3% and the pump efficiency is 39.8%. In the Balance and Main Results sections, you can see the monthly global radiation values, the pumped water value, and other general information. In the winter months, due to low water consumption, the energy generated by the system is not used, which leads to large energy losses. However, there will be no water loss in these months. In addition, an energy loss diagram is also generated, and you can see the full information on it in Figure 4.

Figure 4. General loss diagram.

4. CONCLUSION

Bu summarizing it should be suggested that from the obtained results, it can be concluded that the efficiency of such a system is 17.3% and the efficiency of the pump is almost 40%. The energy below the sag limit is the most important among the various energy losses, covering 78.44% of the total losses. This shows that it is important to assemble the system from compatible parts. Let us present the overall results obtained in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Project, system and results summary.

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